

The Behaviour of the Hydrochlorides of Organic Bases towards Chloroauric Acid. On the Constitution of the Abnormal Auric Chloride Complexes.

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Fenner and Tafel (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3220) have found that the hydrochlorides of piperidine, quinoline, isopropylamine and 2:5-dimethylpyrrolidine react with auric chloride in two different ways under different conditions forming two types of complex compounds, one being represented by the formula $X(AuCl_4)$ (I) while the other is represented by $X_2(AuCl_5)$ (II), where X stands for the organic basic radical. The first type of compounds is produced when the reaction takes place in aqueous medium while the second type is generated in alcoholic solution containing free hydrochloric acid. Compounds of the formula $X(AuCl_4)$ are evidently similar to those of the alkali metals, but chlorides of sodium, potassium, etc., produce no complexes of the second type. The latter type of complexes can be represented by either of the following three constitutional formulæ: (1) $X_2(AuCl_5)$, (2) $X(AuCl_4) \cdot XCl$, (3) $AuCl_3 \cdot 2 XCl$. Formula (1) (Fenner and Tafel, *loc. cit.*) can of course be explained on the basis of Werner's theory assuming the valency of gold to be three, the valency of the two extra chlorine atoms being satisfied by the electropositive basic radicals; but then the co-ordination number becomes five which is rather unusual in common auric complexes. Moreover, it is not possible to explain the chemical and physical properties of these compounds on the basis of the above formula.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to throw light on the constitution of these complexes by determination of the molecular conductivity and molecular volume of some of the typical complexes. Incidentally, complexes of different organic bases other than those used by Fenner and Tafel (*loc. cit.*) have also been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the compounds.—Compounds of the types of $X(AuCl_4)$ and $X_2(AuCl_5)$ have been prepared exactly by following the method of Fenner and Tafel (*loc. cit.*), only chloroauric acid has been used in place of auric chloride. The hydrochlorides of organic bases employed were quinoline, piperidine, ethylamine, benzylamine and trimethylamine. The complexes of the first two were already prepared by the above investigators who were, however, unable to prepare

compounds of the type $X_2(AuCl_5)$ with the hydrochlorides of some of the organic bases. The author also failed to prepare compounds of this type with benzylamine and trimethylamine hydrochlorides, only the normal compounds being prepared both in aqueous and alcoholic solutions. Ethylamine hydrochloride, however, behaved like the hydrochlorides of quinoline, piperidine, etc., and an abnormal compound was obtained from alcoholic solution containing hydrochloric acid. The formation of these two types of complexes does not depend on the concentration of the reactants; it entirely depends upon the medium. The same normal salt, $X(AuCl_4)$ always formed in aqueous medium by varying the concentration of the reactants, but the maximum yield was obtained by treating chloroauric acid with molecular proportions of the basic hydrochlorides. Similarly the same compound $X_2(AuCl_5)$ formed by varying the concentration of the reactants in alcoholic hydrochloric acid medium, maximum yield being obtained with twice the molecular proportion of basic hydrochloride per molecule of chloroauric acid. The second type of compounds was also obtained by heating an alcoholic solution of $X(AuCl_4)$ in presence of hydrochloric acid. The composition of the complexes are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Compounds.	Formulae.	M. p.	Found.	Theoretical
Quinolinium auric chloride	$C_9H_8N^+(AuCl_4)$	236°	Au, 41.98% Cl, 29.85	42 % 30.28
Quinolinium auric chloride-quinolinium chloride	$C_9H_8N(AuCl_4) \cdot C_9H_8NCl$	180°	Au, 31.12 Cl, 27.76	31.05 27.97
Piperidinium auric chloride	$C_5H_{12}N(AuCl_4)$	206°	Au, 46.38 Cl, 33.28	46.35 33.41
Piperidinium auric chloride-piperidinium chloride	$C_5H_{12}N(AuCl_4) \cdot C_5H_{12}NCl$	* 183°	Au, 36.02 Cl, 32.46 N, 5.13	36.05 32.48 5.12
Ethylammonium auric chloride	$C_2H_8N(AuCl_4)$	195°	Au, 50.89 Cl, 35.92	51.17 36.09
Ethylammonium auric chloride-ethylammonium chloride	$C_2H_8N(AuCl_4) \cdot C_2H_8NCl$	70°	Au, 42.6 Cl, 37.78	42.2 38.05
Benzylammonium auric chloride	$C_7H_{10}N(AuCl_4)$	168°	Au, 44.19 Cl, 31.98	44.07 31.77
Trimethylammonium auric chloride	$C_3H_{10}N(AuCl_4)$	220°	Au, 49.4 Cl, 35.42	49.37 35.6

* The melting point of $C_5H_{12}N(AuCl_4) \cdot C_5H_{12}NCl$, recorded by Fenner and Tafel (*loc. cit.*) was 170°, much lower than the actual melting point of the substance probably due to the presence of some impurities in the compound prepared by these authors.

Determination of conductivity and molecular volume.—The following tables contain the results of specific resistances of the complexes of types $X(\text{AuCl}_4)$ and $X_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ and of an equimolecular mixture of $X(\text{AuCl}_4)$ and $X\text{Cl}$ and also of the molecular volumes of $X\text{Cl}$, $X(\text{AuCl}_4)$ and $X_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ when X represents either a piperidinium or a quinolinium radical.

TABLE II.

Base quinoline.

Sp. resistances observed in alcoholic solution at 31°.

Conc. in m. moles/litre ...	5	2.5	1.25	0.625	0.3125
Quinolinium auric chloride-quinolinium chloride ...	211	352	583	949	1445
Equimol. mixture of quinolinium auric chloride and quinolinium chloride ...	212	351	582	949	1445

TABLE III.

Base piperidine.

Sp. resistances observed in alcoholic solution at 25°.

Conc. in m. moles/litre ...	10	5	2.5	1.25
Piperidinium auric chloride-piperidinium chloride ...	137	238	407	705
Equimol. mixture of piperidinium auric chloride and piperidinium chloride ...	141	239	408	706

TABLE IV.

Base quinoline.

Molecular volumes at 25°. Sp. gr. determined in xylene medium.

	Auric chloride.	Quinolinium chloride.	Auric chloride & quinolinium chloride calc.	Quinolinium auric chloride obs.	Quinolinium auric chloride & quinolinium chloride.	
					calc.	obs.
Sp. gr.	4.3	1.45	—	1.91	—	1.762
Mol. vol.	70	114.1	184.1	245	359.1	360

TABLE V.

Base piperidine,

Molecular volumes at 25°. Sp. gr. determined in xylene medium.

	Auric chloride.	Piperidinium chloride.	Auric chloride and piperidinium chloride calc.	Piperidinium auric chloride observed.	Piperidinium auric chloride and piperidinium chloride.	
					calc.	obs.
Sp. gr.	4.9	1.28	—	1.837	—	1.679
Mol. vol.	70	95	165	231.3	326.3	325.5

DISCUSSION.

Compounds of the type $X_2(AuCl_5)$ are unstable in an aqueous or acetone medium. Though they are soluble and fairly stable in cold alcohol, they decompose in hot alcoholic medium, $X(AuCl_4)$ being one of the products of decomposition in each case. They are very stable in alcohol containing free hydrochloric acid even at the boiling temperature. When the yellow salts $X_2(AuCl_5)$ were treated with a little acetone, they gradually turned white, the white crystals were separated, and identified to be the corresponding basic hydrochlorides which being sparingly soluble in acetone separated out, while the more soluble $X(AuCl_4)$ remained in a state of solution. On the other hand, when the salts were treated with water, the more soluble basic hydrochloride went into solution leaving the less soluble normal salt in the undissolved state. The separation of the two components under these two conditions was nearly quantitative. It was also possible to make the two components $X(AuCl_4)$ and XCl combine together by warming the equimolecular quantities of the two salts in alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

The molecular weights of some of the salts were determined by the previous authors (*loc. cit.*) in alcoholic solution by the ebullioscopic method and it was noticed that in the case of piperidinium chloride and piperidinium auric chloride, the observed molecular weights were in agreement with their theoretical values within the limits of experimental error, but that of the abnormal salt, $X_2(AuCl_5)$ was found to be nearly half of the actual value as calculated from

the formula. This might probably be due to the decomposition of the complex salt into the constituent molecules because of its unstability under the experimental conditions.

The easy decomposition of the $\text{AuCl}_3, 2\text{XCl}$ into the two components $\text{X} \cdot \text{AuCl}_4$ and XCl even by the simple addition of water or acetone or molecular weight data cannot be explained by $\text{X}_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$. From our results on molecular volumes and specific resistances it is evident that the compounds $\text{X}_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ should be represented as a molecular compound of the type $\text{X}(\text{AuCl}_4), \text{XCl}$, because it was noticed that the formation of complexes like $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}(\text{AuCl}_4)$ and $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{N}(\text{AuCl}_4)$ were attended by an expansion in volume, nearly 33% in the first case and 40% in the second, whereas the formation of $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{N}(\text{AuCl}_4) \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{NCl}$ or the corresponding quinolinium chloride derivative was not attended with any alteration in volume. When the molecular volumes and specific resistances of XCl and $\text{X}(\text{AuCl}_4)$ are added, the values are found to be equal to those of $\text{X}_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ complexes.

Thus it is definitely established that of the two molecules of XCl linked to each molecule of AuCl_3 , in $\text{X}_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ or $\text{AuCl}_3, 2\text{XCl}$, one forms a complex $\text{X}(\text{AuCl}_4)$ which itself forms a molecular compound with the second molecule of XCl .

SUMMARY.

1. The normal and abnormal salts of auric chloride and piperidinium, quinolinium, and ethylammonium salts have been prepared. The normal salts only have been obtained in the case of benzylammonium and trimethylammonium chlorides.

2. Complexes of the type $\text{X}_2(\text{AuCl}_5)$ named as abnormal auric chlorides of gold have been shown to be molecular compounds of the type $\text{X}(\text{AuCl}_4), \text{XCl}$.

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